

The Undeniable Right to Healthcare in Bangladesh: A Contextual Analysis

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Abstract: Few would contest that living a full and active life depends on being in good health. It is the secret to prosperity and wealth. While poor health is the primary cause of poverty, good health directly supports economic growth. However, one of the most important components of socioeconomic justice and human dignity is the right to healthcare. Bangladesh has ratified numerous conventions protecting this right as a member of the international community. Nonetheless, there are persistent barriers to the country's successful implementation of healthcare rights including poor infrastructure, unequal access, and a lack of enforcement. This paper examines Bangladesh's indisputable right to healthcare from a legal, constitutional, and global perspective. Alongside, it offers suggestions for enhancing healthcare justice while talking about judicial interpretations, remedies, and limitations.

Keywords: Bangladesh; Constitution; Healthcare; Human Rights; Remedies.

1. Introduction: Everyone agrees that access to healthcare is essential to human rights. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines health as a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being.¹ Providing healthcare is a fundamental state duty under both domestic and international law, in addition to being a matter of medical necessity.

The right to healthcare is crucial for upholding justice, equality, and dignity in Bangladesh, where socioeconomic divides are glaring. Additionally, the right to health is directly considered by the World Health Organization and other international instruments. Nowadays, every nation on the planet is a signatory to at least one of the numerous international agreements that recognize health as a fundamental human right². It is noteworthy, one must be in good health in order to enjoy the right to live in peace.

The People's Republic of Bangladesh's Constitution protects this right to health. Anyone in Bangladesh who is denied the opportunity to enjoy life may seek legal action to uphold their rights. In light of international human rights commitments, constitutional guarantees, legal remedies, and court rulings, this essay investigates Bangladesh's indisputable right to healthcare.

2. Literature Review:

The right to healthcare has been a widely discussed topic in the literature of scholars and policy-makers in Bangladesh. Academics believe that healthcare is a fundamental human right that is not only crucial to sustainable development but also human dignity, but a social service. The importance of public health is identified in Articles 15 and 18 of the Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh that prescribes the State to meet the basic medical requirements of all citizens. However, due to the inclusion of these clauses in the Directive Principles of State Policy (Part II of the Constitution), they cannot be judicated, and they depend on the political will instead of being supported by the rights that are legally binding (Haque, 2020). To make the right to health more justiciable in specific court proceedings, legal scholars and rights-based activists often apply it to the wider context of the constitutional right to life under Article 32 of the Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (Joarder et al., 2019).

The National Health Policy (2011) has laid down the foundation towards the right to healthcare by focusing on primary healthcare, maternal and child health, and prevention. Although the policy follows all the principles of the Universal Health Coverage (UHC), the absence of funds, the shortage of medical staff, and the inability to coordinate the work of various health departments remain obstacles to the successful implementation of the policy (Government of Bangladesh, 2011). Research shows that while Bangladesh has made great strides in lowering infant and maternal mortality rates, disparities in access to healthcare still exist in both rural and urban areas, especially for low-income and marginalized groups (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). Numerous families are still forced below the poverty line due to high out-of-pocket expenses (OOP), which compromises the affordability component of the right to health (Joarder et al., 2019).

Research shows that rural communities do not receive equitable or high-quality medical care. Urban areas usually have better facilities and professional expertise than rural communities, which primarily rely on unlicensed and informal healthcare providers (Haque, 2020). The increasing prevalence of noncommunicable diseases, environmental factors and occupational health issues have given rise to a new dimension of healthcare inequality. Research indicates that if public health governance lacks adequate funding, oversight and transparency, constitutional recognition alone cannot guarantee effective healthcare rights (WHO, 2020).

Over time, judicial decisions have influenced the way law perceives healthcare as a fundamental right. Numerous legal rulings, including those ensuring that prisoners have access to emergency departments and medical care, indicate that judges are increasingly dedicated to upholding health rights within the broader context of human dignity and the right to life (The Daily Star, 2023). Nevertheless, such interventions are relatively narrow and focused and fail to make a substantial difference in policy changes (BLAST, 2022). The civil society and lobby groups continue to urge the government to increase the amount of money spent on health care and hold those concerned accountable.

Healthcare is not only a service but also one of the most essential human functions which is critical to well being as it is emphasized by researchers such as Paul Hunt (2004) and Amartya Sen (1999). Hunt operationalizes the right to health into the AAAQ principles of availability, accessibility, acceptability, and quality which provides a legal and ethical framework through which healthcare systems assessment is conducted. The disparity in healthcare access is higher in the rural setting and among the marginalized groups, which is proven by the study conducted in Bangladesh (Awal, 2018). Furthermore, the studies depict that judicial activism has played a critical role in the interpretation of the constitutional stipulations that incorporate the aspect of healthcare in the right to life. To sum up, the literature review assessment provides a refined opinion on the progress of Bangladesh in respect of obtaining the intrinsic right to healthcare. Even though there has been a great progress in the indicators of health and commitments in statutes, inequity in funding, access, and equity remain the obstacles in achieving a universal health care. This research study will focus on the legal, policy and practical context of healthcare rights and the Bangladesh socioeconomic and constitutional context.

3. Objectives of the Study:

The main aims of the research include:

1. To compare the conceptual framework of the right to healthcare in the international human rights law and the provisions in the Bangladesh con-

stitution.

2. To assess available legal remedies, judicial interpretations and institutional mechanisms that can help curb the right to healthcare in Bangladesh.
3. To explore historic cases that have influenced the establishment and implementation of healthcare rights.
4. To determine loopholes, issues, and constraints in the effective implementation of healthcare rights to every citizen.
5. To make policy, legal, and institutional recommendations to guarantee the equitable and effective access to healthcare in Bangladesh.

4. Research Questions:

The following are the questions that will be answered in this study:

1. What is the conceptualization of the right to healthcare in the international human rights law and Bangladesh Constitution?
2. Which are the legal solutions that exist in Bangladesh to safeguard the right to healthcare?
3. To what extent have historic court cases influenced the application of the rights to healthcare in Bangladesh?
4. Which policy and legal suggestions may enhance healthcare access and fairness in Bangladesh?

5. Methodology:

This study is in a qualitative, doctrinal direction:

Document Analysis: The review of the Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, the legislation (Consumer Rights protection Act, Penal Code, Medical Dental Council Act), and Government policies.

Case Law Analysis: In which the judicial rulings are identified and examined to reveal how the right to healthcare is interpreted and applied by the court.

Comparative Perspective: To put the obligations of Bangladesh in perspective, the international conventions (UDHR, ICESCR, ICCPR, CRC, CEDAW) are analyzed.

Analytical Framework: Summarizing the literature, legal and jurisprudence findings to pinpoint gaps, problems and recommendations to take. Under this methodology, it is possible to gain a holistic concept of both the legal theory and the pragmatic implementation of healthcare rights in Bangladesh.

6. The Concept of Right to Healthcare:

The right to healthcare is a universal human right that has been universally established as an inherent right to both international law and in the academic field. It is the overall promotion of physical, psychological and social welfare and not just the lack of illness. It is a concept that has been closely examined by eminent scholars and the idea has been clothed in numerous international documents. The Constitution of the WHO clearly states as follows, The highest attainable standard of health is one of the basic rights of all human beings. This definition does not only cover medical services, but extends to the more far-reaching aspects that influence health, such as a secure environment and the ability to live well. This definition includes more than just medical services; it also includes the larger factors that affect health, like a safe environment and good living conditions. This is because it is full and includes physical, mental and social well-being. Furthermore, the right to health is established within the larger framework of an adequate standard of living by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), a seminal document in international human rights law. "Everyone has the right to a standard

of living necessary for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing, medical care, and necessary social services," in accordance with Article 25(1)⁵. This formulation emphasizes healthcare's role in guaranteeing a life of dignity by inextricably linking it to other basic human needs. Furthermore, Amartya Sen, the Nobel laureate, applies his capability approach—a framework that measures well-being in terms of an individual's capacity to accomplish specific "functionings" and "capabilities"—to the right to health. According to Sen, being healthy and preventing early death and morbidity are essential capabilities⁴. So, access to healthcare is more than just a service, it's a necessary part of giving people more freedom and a better chance of living a happy life. The concept of the right to healthcare is a multifaceted and evolving premise that has transitioned from mere access to medical care to an extensive framework that considers the social, economic, and political determinants of health. It is a fundamental human right, enshrined in international conventions and supported by robust scholarly analysis, demanding both state-level and global action to ensure its realization for all.

7. Human Rights in International Conventions Regarding the Right to Healthcare: The right to healthcare is expressly recognized by a number of international conventions. Bangladesh has acceded to or ratified numerous of these:

7. 1. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) 1948: The right to a living standard adequate for one's health is affirmed in Article 25 of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights.⁵

7. 2. The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) 1966: Everyone is entitled to the highest degree of physical and mental well-being, as stated in Article 12 of the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights⁶.

7. 3. The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR): The right to healthcare is directly impacted by several of the ICCPR's provisions, even though its main focus is on civil and political rights. One interpretation of the right to life (Article 6) holds that states must provide basic medical care, particularly when doing otherwise would endanger life.⁷

7. 4. The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) 1989: In 1990, Bangladesh ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child, which mandates that states offer healthcare and medical assistance to all children.⁸

7. 5. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) 1979: According to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, women have guaranteed access to reproductive healthcare services⁹.

As a result, the state of Bangladesh is obligated by its international obligations to gradually establish healthcare as a human right.

8. Human Rights and Fundamental Rights in Bangladesh Regarding the Right to Healthcare: Although it does not specifically acknowledge healthcare as a fundamental right, the Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh does contain several pertinent provisions pertaining to this topic in its second section, the Fundamental Principles of State Policy, and its third section, Fundamental Rights. They are as follows: **Article 15:** Acknowledges that the state has a basic duty to provide for basic needs, including health care¹⁰.

Article 18 (1): Declares that the state's top priority is to improve nutrition and public health¹¹.

Article 32: Guarantees the right to life and personal freedom, which courts have construed to encompass the right to health¹².

Article 44 and 102: Make the High Court Division's enforcement of fundamental rights possible¹³.

As a result, although enforcement is still restricted, the right to healthcare is implied within larger fundamental rights.

9. Existing Remedies in Bangladesh Regarding the Right to Healthcare: There isn't a single healthcare law in Bangladesh. Rather, remedies are sought under a number of current statutes. Among the most pertinent are:

Civil suit for compensation: The aggrieved and his family can sue for damages under 'Law of Tort'¹⁴.

Criminal Charges: Sections of the Penal Code, 1860, allow for the charging of medical professionals. In particular, sections 336 to 338—causing bodily injury by negligence; section 312—causing a miscarriage; section 304A—for causing death by negligence; etc¹⁵.

The Consumer Rights Protection Act, 2009: In cases involving healthcare, such as medical negligence, victims may bring a lawsuit under the Consumer Rights Protection Act of 2009.

Because it views patients as "consumers" of services, this is crucial. The Act's Sections 52 and 53 permit compensation requests¹⁶.

Therefore, remedies for carelessness or malpractice in healthcare services are provided by the Consumer Rights Protection Act of 2009.

Constitutional Law: Right to life is protected by Article 32 of the People's Republic of Bangladesh Constitution. Also, a Public Interest Litigation (PIL) or writ petition may be filed before the Supreme Court of Bangladesh's High Court Division to contest any infringement of this right¹⁷.

Judicial Review: According to Article 102 of the Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, the High Court Division of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh permits the filing of writ petitions or Public Interest Litigation (PIL) in relation to healthcare issues¹⁸.

Public Interest Litigation (PIL): One type of legal action is a Public Interest Litigation (PIL), in which a person or organization seeks redress for the benefit of the public rather than for personal gain. Organizations and individuals may request judicial intervention for violations of healthcare rights under Article 102.

The Bangladesh Medical and Dental Council Act 2010: It controls the standards for professional healthcare¹⁹.

National Human Rights Commission (NHRC): It gets complaints about people not getting healthcare²⁰.

Government Health Schemes: Even though they are frequently criticized for their inefficiency, government health initiatives like maternal health programs and community clinics also function as corrective measures.

10. Significant Cases Pertaining to the Right to Healthcare in Bangladesh: The case law of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh has significantly shaped the legal recognition of the right to healthcare in the country. Although the Bangladeshi Constitution does not explicitly designate healthcare as a fundamental right, the judiciary has construed many sections to encompass access to healthcare services, particularly those pertaining to the rights of equality, life, and human dignity. Numerous significant cases illustrate this trend in the judiciary.

Dr. Mohiuddin Farooque v. Bangladesh and Others (1996), commonly

known as the FAP 20 case, acknowledged that the right to life under Article 32 of the Constitution encompasses the right to healthcare and a healthy environment, while also expanding the definition of locus standi in public interest litigation. The Court concluded that the fulfillment of all human faculties, including necessary medical care for dignity, falls under the right to life, which extends beyond mere animal existence

Advocate Syed Saifuddin Kamal v. Bangladesh (2000): In this case, the High Court Division intervened to address the lack of restrictions in private medical practices and institutions. The Court²³ highlighted the State's fundamental duty to improve public health and provide for basic requirements under Part II (Fundamental Principles of State Policy), notably Articles 15 and 18.

Bangladesh Legal Aid and Services Trust (BLAST) v. Bangladesh (2011): Custodial deaths brought on by subpar medical care in prisons were the subject of this case. The Court determined that withholding medical treatment from inmates violated both Article 32, which protects the right to life and personal liberty, and Article 35, which protects against cruel, inhuman, or degrading punishment²¹. The ruling upheld the claim that the state has a positive duty to guarantee healthcare access because it is essential to human dignity.

Ain o Salish Kendra (ASK) v. Bangladesh (2013): The court took into account the government hospitals' inability to offer emergency medical care. It reaffirmed that access to healthcare is an essential part of the constitutional right to life and instructed the state to take steps to hold healthcare providers accountable²².

Rahib Reza v. Labaid Hospital Ltd. (2010): The case of Rahib Reza v. Labaid Hospital Ltd. is a watershed moment in Bangladesh's medical negligence jurisprudence. The petitioner claimed that Labaid Hospital was very careless and that this caused his wife's death after she received bad care. The High Court Division accepted the writ petition under Article 102 of the Constitution, ruling that medical negligence is not just a private wrong, but also a violation of basic rights, such as the right to life and personal freedom under Articles 31 and 32.

The Court said that private healthcare providers are not above the law when they refuse people the right treatment, even if they are in business to generate money. It said that private hospitals should be regulated and that there should be ways to hold people accountable when they make medical mistakes.

The Paracetamol Cases of 2022: The High Court Division's verdict in several cases where more than 100 children died from paracetamol syrup that had been tainted was a turning point in Bangladesh's history of public health law. The court made a historic ruling that was very important for the public interest and was specifically concerning the state's commitment to its citizens. The court made it plain that "Every citizen of Bangladesh has the right to free medical care as a basic constitutional right."

This ruling made two key rules: everyone has the right to clean medicine, and the Constitution says that the government must give medical care to all citizens. The court's decision to give money to the victims' families made it increasingly evident that the courts are in charge of making sure that regulatory bodies are held accountable for their mistakes. These examples indicate how the courts have included the right to healthcare to the greater list of human rights by interpreting constitutional rights in a more current fashion. Although these decisions have not yet resulted in full statutory recognition of healthcare as a justiciable fundamental right, they provide strong jurisprudential support for its enforcement.

11. Major Findings: Thomas Pogge, a philosopher, contends that denying people access to healthcare is a type of "institutional harm" for which there is a worldwide responsibility, especially when it comes to global poverty²³. His viewpoint emphasizes states' moral and legal duties to not only treat their own citizens but also to change international organizations that support poverty and jeopardize the health and welfare of underprivileged groups everywhere.

Nonetheless, international law recognizes the right to healthcare, and Bangladesh's Constitution provides some indirect protection for this right. The following are some of the main findings and analyses:

1. Constitutional interpretations have been expanded to include healthcare due to judicial activism.
2. Marginalized groups are disproportionately affected by healthcare inequality.
3. Working toward the full realization of the right to health becomes a legally and morally binding obligation when international instruments such as the ICESCR are ratified.
4. By using Public Interest Litigation (PIL) to hold the government responsible for shortcomings in environmental and public health protection, the judiciary has demonstrated a progressive and proactive approach.
5. Even though these court decisions have been made, the right to health is still not being fully realized because of other practical problems, such as how resources are distributed, how weak institutions are, and how corrupt the system is.

12. Discussion:

The right to healthcare is acknowledged in article 32 of the Constitution of the People Republic of Bangladesh. This is an indication that Bangladesh is concerned with the issue of public health. Although this right is legally accepted, it is not being applied equally and uniformly. Although national policies such as the National Health Policy (2011) provide the legal and policy background of the healthcare delivery, the gap between the law and its practice still exists. This demonstrates that there are issues with the manner in which things are configured, inadequate resources and the manner in which things are operated.

Access to healthcare services is very uneven in terms of the location and the amount of money. There are normally hospitals in cities that are equipped with the right equipment and specialized medical services. Rural regions, on the other hand, usually lack sufficient skilled professionals or healthcare centers. Money problems worsen these differences. As an example, expensive out-of-pocket may provide disadvantages to people with low income to gain health care and, therefore, provide disadvantages to all to receive the same level of care. Gender inequality also complicates access to healthcare among women who usually have to contend with logistical and social obstacles that complicate the process of accessing the said care.

Quality of healthcare services and infrastructure remains a major issue. In some cases, there are not sufficient staff, medical equipment or patients in the public institutions, particularly in the rural areas. The private sector has more services, yet the segregation of the rich and the poor people has not changed due to the distribution inequalities and expensive. Organized approaches work, the efficiency of communal wellbeing programs like immunization programs and maternity and childcare programs. However, their general success is hampered by the lapses in

coverage, lack of regular performance and oversight.

The socioeconomic factors have a significant influence on health outcomes especially employment, education and financial resources. Individuals are impoverished, including migrants, slum residents and informal laborers, are more susceptible to structural issues. The assistance that individuals receive is typically insufficient. People struggle to fully exercise their right to health due to cultural norms and a lack of health literacy, which in turn complicates their access to medical care.

The government is collaborating with non-profit organizations and international organizations such as UNICEF and WHO to provide assistance to individuals residing in impoverished regions. These programs are beneficial for the health of individuals; however, they do not address the most significant issues within the healthcare system of the nation. The full enjoyment of one's healthcare liberties is impeded by institutional, policy, and cultural barriers in Bangladesh. The disparities are further exacerbated by bureaucratic issues, inadequate resource management, inadequate health financing and inadequate enforcement. Some social and cultural problems that stop people from getting the care they need are not knowing enough about health, being ashamed and being afraid of foreigners.

To overcome these issues, it is very important to put smart policy ideas into action. To make healthcare more affordable and efficient, we need to work on primary healthcare system, push for universal healthcare, and make the most of public private partnerships. It is also very important to enhance the laws and strict mechanisms of accountability to make sure that constitutional promises lead to measurable improvements in health care.

Bangladesh's policies are consistent, but they don't always follow international human rights norms like the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR). We need to get rid of these problems so that the constitutional right to health care is more than just a legal idea.

12. Limitations:

There are number of limitations that can be found during this study, which are as follows:

1. Healthcare is not expressly recognized as a fundamental right in the constitution.
2. Inadequate application of current health regulations.
3. Insufficient infrastructure for healthcare, particularly in rural areas.
4. Dearth procedures for medical negligence accountability.

13. Recommendations: Paul Hunt is a prominent expert on the right to health and a former Special Rapporteur for the UN. Through the "right to health framework," which identifies four essential, interconnected components that governments must guarantee—the availability, accessibility, acceptability, and quality of health facilities, goods, and services—he operationalized this right²⁴. Hunt's work shows that the right to health is not merely an aspirational goal, but a legal necessity that requires states to take specific, measurable acts, including giving out resources and setting up open, non-discriminatory health systems. Therefore, the relevant authorities ought to recommend the following:

1. By amending the constitution, we can acknowledge healthcare as a fundamental right that can be challenged.
2. Increase funding for healthcare, particularly in rural regions.

3. Create impartial tribunals for medical negligence.
4. Inform the public of their rights in healthcare.
5. ICCPR, ICESCR, and other ratified treaties should be reflected in domestic legislation.
6. Hospital administration and management ought to be incorporated into a centralized regulatory framework.
7. Patients should be provided with the accurate information and accountability and transparency should be ensured.
8. Digital healthcare systems ought to be reinforced in order to provide need-based healthcare to the outlying areas.
9. To ensure that the public health organizations conduct the relevant research and make meaningful contributions to the decision-making process, they must be strengthened.
10. A good system of monitoring should be established to ensure that the private hospitals and clinics are effectively regulated.
11. The complaint procedures to be found in different laws should be made accessible to the public.
12. The existing schedules depicting the price of medical services should be updated immediately.

Concluding Remarks: In Bangladesh, there are still efforts to have a full enactment of the right to health. Lack of a clear constitutional provision is a major setback; but the liberal and broad-minded interpretations by the courts have actually transformed health into a policy goal to an enforceable right. The judicial system is strong, as a result of the judicial activity and commitments of other states. The second step is to bridge the gap between the law and reality. Adhering to the recommendations, Bangladesh can be a step closer to establishing the society where all its citizens would enjoy the health care that is as big as possible.

Endnotes

1. World Health Organization, Preamble to the Constitution of the World Health Organization as adopted by the International Health Conference, New York, 19–22 June 1946 (1946).
2. Paul Hunt, 'The Right to Health: An Overview' in Audrey Chapman (ed), *The Right to Health: A Reader* (Routledge 2004) 5.
3. Universal Declaration of Human Rights (adopted 10 December 1948) UNGA Res 217 A(III), art 25(1).
4. Amartya Sen, *Development as Freedom* (Anchor Books 1999) 75.
5. Universal Declaration of Human Rights (n 4).
6. International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (adopted 16 December 1966, entered into force 3 January 1976) 993 UNTS 3, art 12.
7. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (adopted 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976) 999 UNTS 171, art 6.
8. Convention on the Rights of the Child (adopted 20 November 1989, entered into force 2 September 1990) 1577 UNTS 3, art 24.
9. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (adopted 18 December 1979, entered into force 3 September 1981) 1249 UNTS 13, art 12.
10. Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh 1972, art 15.
11. Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (n 11), art 18(1).
12. Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (n 11), art 32.
13. Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (n 11), arts 44, 102.
14. MA Awal, 'Medical Malpractice in Bangladesh and the Right to Health' (2018) 5(1) *Journal of Law and Development* 1, 10.
15. Penal Code 1860 (Act No XLV of 1860), ss 304A, 312, 336–338.
16. Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009 (Act No 26 of 2009), ss 52, 53.
17. Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (n 11), art 32.

18. Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (n 11), art 102.
19. Bangladesh Medical and Dental Council Act 2010 (Act No 53 of 2010).
20. National Human Rights Commission Act 2009 (Act No 53 of 2009), s 12.
21. *Bangladesh Legal Aid and Services Trust (BLAST) v Bangladesh and Others* 63 DLR (2011) 259.
22. *Ain o Salish Kendra (ASK) v Bangladesh and Others* (Writ Petition No 13575 of 2013) [Unreported].
23. Thomas Pogge, *World Poverty and Human Rights: Cosmopolitan Responsibilities and Reforms* (Polity Press 2002) 15–20.
24. Paul Hunt, 'The Right to the Highest Attainable Standard of Health: What Does it Mean?' (2005) 1(1) *Health and Human Rights* 1, 3.

Bibliography

A. International Treaties and Conventions

- Constitution of the World Health Organization (adopted 22 July 1946, entered into force 7 April 1948) 14 UNTS 185
- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (adopted 18 December 1979, entered into force 3 September 1981) 1249 UNTS 13
- Convention on the Rights of the Child (adopted 20 November 1989, entered into force 2 September 1990) 1577 UNTS 3
- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (adopted 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976) 999 UNTS 171
- International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (adopted 16 December 1966, entered into force 3 January 1976) 993 UNTS 3
- Universal Declaration of Human Rights (adopted 10 December 1948) UNGA Res 217 A(III)

B. Legislation (Bangladesh)

- Bangladesh Medical and Dental Council Act 2010 (Act No 53 of 2010)
- Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh 1972
- Consumer Rights Protection Act 2009 (Act No 26 of 2009)
- National Human Rights Commission Act 2009 (Act No 53 of 2009)
- Penal Code 1860 (Act No XLV of 1860)

C. Cases

- *Advocate Syed Saifuddin Kamal v Bangladesh and Others* 52 DLR (2000) 50
- *Ain o Salish Kendra (ASK) v Bangladesh and Others* (Writ Petition No 13575 of 2013) [Unreported]
- *Bangladesh Legal Aid and Services Trust (BLAST) v Bangladesh and Others* 63 DLR (2011) 259
- *Dr Mohiuddin Farooque v Bangladesh and Others* 48 DLR (1996) 438
- *Rahib Reza v Labaid Hospital Ltd* (Writ Petition No 9138 of 2010) [Unreported]
- *The Paracetamol Cases* (High Court Division) [Unreported, 2022]

D. Secondary Sources

- Awal MA, 'Medical Malpractice in Bangladesh and the Right to Health' (2018) 5(1) *Journal of Law and Development* 1
- Hunt P, 'The Right to Health: An Overview' in Audrey Chapman (ed), *The Right to Health: A Reader* (Routledge 2004)
- Hunt P, 'The Right to the Highest Attainable Standard of Health: What Does it Mean?' (2005) 1 (1) *Health and Human Rights* 1
- Pogge T, *World Poverty and Human Rights: Cosmopolitan Responsibilities and Reforms* (Polity Press 2002)
- Sen A, *Development as Freedom* (Anchor Books 1999)